

HEMP REINFORCED BIOBASED POLYURETHANES FOR AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS: EVALUATION OF THERMOMECHANICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

In recent decades, polymeric composite materials have received a lot of attention. Indeed, there is an increasing drive towards lightweight, durable and cost effective compounds for sector such as automotive market. Polyurethanes are among polymers finding increasing applications in automotive sector. Indeed, in 2000, more than 900,000 tons of polyurethanes were used by vehicle manufacturers. Owing to the versatility of polyurethanes chemistry, a broad range of properties and applications are possible, such as seat pans, sun shades, door panels, package trays and truck box panels.

Recently, natural fibers have been considered as substitute for glass fibers by the automotive industry. Advantage of this replacement are reduction of cost, low density of resulting composites, acceptable specific strength properties, enhanced energy recovery, carbon dioxide balance, and biodegradability.

Polyurethanes are made from petroleum based polyols and isocyanates. Although "Isocyanates" are not yet made from renewable resources; the formulations of polyols from renewable resources have attracted a lot of interest from various groups of researchers. Biobased polyurethanes are already produced from castor oil. However, soybean oil is more interesting from the economic standpoint since it is produced in appreciable amounts in United States.

At the Composite Materials and Structures Center of the Michigan State University, we are working on the development of new polyurethane composites for automotive applications based on renewable resources. Our aim is to use polyols derived from plant oils and natural fibers.

Polyol made from soybean oil, soy phosphate ester (hydroxyl number 139 mg KOH/g) (ATOFINA), is used and combined with aromatic isocyanate (pMDI). Polyurethane resin of an average density of 1.13 g/cm³ and an average T_g of 95.6°C shows a storage modulus (G') of 1354 MPa at 30°C (DMA). Upon loading with 20 wt % of hemp (raw or sized) fiber, biocomposites with improved thermo-mechanical properties are obtained. Indeed, glass transition temperatures (T_g) higher than 110°C and G' exceeding 2000 MPa are observed. In comparison, E-glass (20 wt %) reinforced composites do not show improved T_g for an average value of G' of 3532 MPa. It is thought that chemical bonding between the isocyanate groups with the hydroxyl groups of both the polyol and the fiber contribute to the property enhancement.

KEYWORDS: Biobased polyurethane, soybean phosphate ester polyol, hemp, thermo-mechanical properties, biocomposites

INTRODUCTION

Recent years have seen a growing interest in the development of bio-based products that can reduce the widespread dependence on fossil fuels. Indeed, the inevitable depletion of petroleum reserves with the attending high cost has prompted researchers to develop polymers from cheap and renewable resources. Polyurethanes (PURs) are usually made from petroleum based polyols and isocyanates and have widespread applications in automotive parts, coatings, sealants, adhesives and other infrastructure uses [1-2]. Today, polyurethanes are finding a growing interest for applications as composites due to the increasing demand for lightweight, durable and cost effective compounds for sector such as automotive market. [3]. Owing to the versatility of polyurethanes chemistry, a broad range of properties and applications are possible for reinforced composites, such as seat pans, sun shades, door panels, package trays and truck box panels. However, the adhesion between the polyurethane matrix and the fiber surface is a key parameter in the improvement of mechanical performances [4-6].

Polyurethanes based on renewable resources can be prepared by reacting a polyol made from a plant oil and an isocyanate. Indeed, castor oil, a hydroxyl rich triglyceride and other plant oils have been used for making polyol functional compounds [7-10]. Among the possible renewable resources useful to make a polyol, soybean oil is of particular interest because of its abundance (ca. 70 millions metric tons/year in USA) and low price (ca. 0.20 \$/lb).

In this study, we investigated the dynamical mechanical properties of polyurethane composites made from soybean ester phosphate polyol (SOPEP). This polyol (ATOFINA, MN) is made by acid hydrolysis of epoxidized soybean oil. Polyurethane thermosets can be prepared from SOPEP and polymeric methylene diphenyl isocyanate (pMDI). Reinforcement of such polyurethane with fibers, natural or synthetic, should improve mechanical properties if a good fiber-matrix adhesion is achieved. We compare a lignocellulosic fiber, i.e. hemp, and E-glass fiber as reinforcements of SOPEP based polyurethanes.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials. Soybean phosphate ester polyol was received from ATOFINA. Baydur 410 IMR aromatic isocyanate (pMDI) was a gift from Bayer. Pure hemp mat was received from Flaxcraft (NJ) and chopped E-glass fiber (1.5 in) mat from Kemlite (IL).

Composite Fabrication. Composites were prepared by first mixing SOPEP and the pMDI. The isocyanate index used was 130 (30 mol% excess of isocyanate groups compared to hydroxyl groups). The mixture was stirred for 2 minutes and laid up on both sides of the fiber mat (5.5 in X 7 in) which was previously dried overnight at 80°C in a vacuum oven. The wetted mats were maintained under vacuum at room temperature to remove trapped gas (ca. 5 minutes) and then compression molded for 10 minutes at 110°C in a Carver® laboratory press to a thickness of 0.1 in. SOPEP based polyurethane and its composites containing 20 wt % of fiber were obtained and postcured at 130°C for 2 hours in an air oven.

Fiber Surface Treatments. During the alkali treatment, hemp mat is immersed in 5wt% NaOH solution for either 1 or 5h at room temperature, followed by washing with conductivity water until pH ~ 6 is achieved. For the graft copolymerization of acrylonitrile, the required amount of fiber mats was vacuum dried prior to the treatment. The dried fiber mat was soaked in a solution containing 3 wt% of acrylonitrile, 0.5 wt% of dicumyl peroxide and 96.5 wt% of ethanol for 15 minutes. The mat was dried overnight in hood after draining out the excess solution. The mats were vacuum dried overnight before using.

Characterization. Specimen densities are determined by the mass to volume equation. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) is performed with a DMA 2980 TA Instruments. Samples were tested in a three-point bending mode at fixed frequency (1Hz) with a heating rate of 5°C/min. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out under nitrogen atmosphere with a Hi-Res. TGA 2950 Thermogravimetric Analyzer at a heating rate of 20°C/min. from 30 to 600°C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Densities of the neat polyurethane and its composites were determined by the classical equation, i.e. the ratio of mass to volume (Fig. 1). Upon hemp fiber loading, the average density does not significantly change with fiber chemical treatment. It ranges from 1.11 to 1.13 g/cm³. However, in the case of reinforcement with E-glass, the average density is clearly higher, i.e. 1.24 g/cm³, due to the higher density of glass compared to hemp (2.6 vs. 1.3 g/cm³).

Figure 1. Density of SOPEP-based polyurethane and composites: A) Neat polyurethane; B) 20 wt% hemp; C) 20 wt% alkali treated 1h hemp; D) Alkali treated 5h; E) Acrylonitrile grafted hemp; F) E-Glass.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) of these soybean based polyurethanes was performed in a three-point bending mode in order to determine thermo-mechanical properties. The temperature dependence of the storage modulus (G') for each specimen was recorded (Fig. 2). In the case of the neat polyurethane, the value of G' was almost constant at low temperature (glassy state) before dropping in the region between 40 and 90°C (glass transition region). As the temperature further increased, G' levels off in the rubbery state. The presence of a region where G' remains relatively constant indicates that a stable crosslinked network exists. The patterns of the curves of temperature dependence for the composite specimens are similar in nature to the neat polyurethane. However, over the temperature range studied, G' is substantially increased upon fiber loading (either for hemp or E-glass) due to the addition of the much stiffer hemp biofiber or glass fibers, therefore increasing the stiffness of the overall material. However, storage modulus is systematically lower over the all range of temperature studied for the composites

containing sized hemp, i.e. alkali treated or acrylonitrile grafted, compared to raw hemp reinforced polyurethane.

Figure 2. Temperature dependence of the storage modulus (G') of SOPEP-based polyurethane and its composites: A) Neat polyurethane; B) 20 w% hemp; C) 20 wt% alkali treated 1h hemp; D) Alkali treated 5h; E) Acrylonitrile grafted hemp; F) E-Glass.

A comparison of the average G' values measured at 30°C is shown in Fig. 3 together with the specific G' ($G' / \text{density}$). At this temperature, specific G' increased from an average of 1199 MPa (SOPEP based polyurethane) to 2937 MPa in the 20 wt % hemp reinforced polyurethane and 2848 MPa when 20 wt % of E-glass is added. It bears mentioning that the error bars overlap thus indicating that the specific G' is the same in both composites. These values represent respective improvements of 145 and 138 % compared to the neat SOPEP based polyurethane. Alkali treatment and acrylonitrile grafting of hemp do not improve G' but lead to lower values yet higher than the neat polyurethane (perhaps due to a softening of the biofiber as a result of the treatment conditions). The average specific G' values are now 2178 and 2077 MPa for respectively the 1 and 5h alkali treated fibers and 2314 MPa for the acrylonitrile grafted one. The improvement is thus of 82, 73 and 93 % in each case. However, error bars overlap suggesting no real difference between those values.

Figure 3. Storage modulus (G') and specific modulus ($G'/\text{density}$) (at 30°C) of SOPEP-based polyurethane and its composites: A) Neat polyurethane; B) 20 w% hemp; C) 20 wt% alkali treated 1h hemp; D) Alkali treated 5h; E) Acrylonitrile grafted hemp; F) E-Glass.

The glass transition temperatures (T_g) were determined from the peak of the tan delta (ratio of loss modulus, G'' , to storage modulus, G') curves (Fig. 4). Only one T_g (95.6°C) was observed for the polyurethane suggesting a single phase system. Upon fiber loading; the T_g of this bio-based polyurethane shifted to higher values and was determined to be 110.6°C for the hemp-reinforced composite, 113.1°C for the 1h alkali treated and 108.6°C for the hemp mat treated for 5h and finally 111.3°C in the acrylonitrile grafted sample. In the case of E-glass, no change in the value of T_g (95.6°C) was noted. The increase in T_g for the hemp polyurethane composites suggests an increase in the degree of crosslinking (with the hydroxyl groups on the hemp fiber surface) and thus a reduction in chain mobility.

Figure 4. Glass transition temperature (T_g) of SOPEP-based polyurethane and its composites: A) Neat polyurethane; B) 20 w% hemp; C) 20 wt% alkali treated 1h hemp; D) Alkali treated 5h; E) Acrylonitrile grafted hemp; F) E-Glass.

In parallel, the intensity of tan delta decreases in all these composites due to the net volume reduction of the polyurethane resin but also due to mobility restriction (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. $\tan \delta$ (loss modulus) of SOPEP-based polyurethane and its composites: A) Neat polyurethane; B) 20 w% hemp; C) 20 wt% alkali treated 1h hemp; D) Alkali treated 5h; E) Acrylonitrile grafted hemp; F) E-Glass.

Good dispersion, efficient wetting and good adhesion at the fiber-matrix interface are requirements for composites with improved mechanical properties [11]. The mechanism responsible for adhesion between the fibers and the polyurethane matrix is not clearly determined. The enhancement of stiffness and T_g in hemp reinforced polyurethane is attributed to good fiber dispersion, efficient wetting and good fiber-matrix adhesion. Adhesion through chemical bonding can be favored since covalent bonds may be formed by reaction of free hydroxyl groups on the surface of the fiber with the isocyanate, as suggested in the literature [12]. Therefore, chemical modification of the surface (i.e. alkali treatment and acrylonitrile grafting) might have a direct influence on the wetting, fiber distribution and the fiber-matrix adhesion. In the case of E-glass composite, a study carried out in our laboratory on the nature of interfacial interactions between polyurethane and glass showed that the contribution of chemical bonding, covalent or ionic, is only slightly important. Formation of an interphase region in which hydrogen bonding plays a key role is more likely to occur in glass reinforced polyurethanes [13-14]. However, further investigations are in the process of being carried out.

Thermal stability was studied by means of thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) under nitrogen. In the case of the neat polyurethane, thermal degradation starts around 320°C and two maximum peaks corresponding to the maximum of thermal degradation are observed at 389 and 483°C, suggesting that at least two mechanisms of degradation are involved. The pattern of curves corresponding to the temperature dependence of the weight loss for composites is presented in Fig. 6. Residual weight at 600°C is about 13 % for the neat polyurethane and a little be higher for its composites with hemp (raw or sized) while in the case of E-Glass composite the value reached is about 34 % (Table 1). This result is not surprising since glass does not degrade while hemp fiber starts to degrade around 300°C.

Figure 6. Temperature dependence of weight loss for of SOPEP-based polyurethane and its composites: A) Neat polyurethane; B) 20 w% hemp; C) 20 wt% alkali treated 1h hemp; D) Acrylonitrile grafted hemp; E) E-Glass.

Two temperatures of maximum thermal degradation were also recorded for each sample of hemp (raw or sized) and E-glass reinforced composites (Table 1). According to data given in that Table, the alkali treated hemp composite is the less stable among all specimens while the maxima of decomposition are slightly shifted to higher values for composites that contain raw hemp and acrylonitrile.

Table 1. Temperature of maximum decomposition (Td) of SOPEP-based polyurethane and its composites.

Entry	Polyurethane sample	Td ₁ (°C)	Td ₂ (°C)	Residual weight (%)
1	Neat	389	483	13.2
2	Raw hemp	391	497	15.1
3	Alkali treated hemp	384	477	16.7
4	Acrylonitrile-g-hemp	394	504	18.3
5	Glass	391	502	34.2

CONCLUSIONS

These results reveal that polyurethane composites reinforced with 20 wt % of either hemp or glass fibers have improved mechanical properties with these soybean-based polyols despite the differences in surface chemical composition and topology of these two fibers. It is worthy to notice that the natural lignocellulosic fiber used, i.e. hemp, proved to be a better reinforcement than E-glass when one considers the higher T_g (by 15°C) and the lower density of the composites but also the price of this fiber (one third that of glass). Surface modification of this fiber, i.e. hemp, such as alkali treatment and acrylonitrile grafting decreases the biocomposite stiffness (perhaps due to a softening of the biofiber) while the glass transition temperature is almost unchanged compared to the non treated hemp mat.

Thermogravimetric analysis shows that presence of hemp slightly enhances thermal degradation for the composites containing raw hemp and alkali treated hemp. While in the case of the acrylonitrile grafted hemp and E-glass reinforced composites thermal degradation is retarded under nitrogen.

The results presented in this paper indicate that biobased polyurethanes reinforced with hemp fibers show improved mechanical properties and can compete with glass reinforced composites. The net advantage lies in the higher glass transition temperature and the lower cost (20-30 cents/lb for raw hemp vs. 90 cents/lb for E-glass) of the hemp composite while comparable stiffness is achieved in both cases.

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